

Survey Questionnaire Protocol

Feedback Practices in Remote and Hybrid Software Development Teams

Section 1

This questionnaire aims to investigate the point of view of professionals on Feedback Practices in software development teams. We investigated how feedback practices are adopted in remote or hybrid software development teams, exploring the negative and positive points of adopting these practices daily, and highlighting the good practices and characteristics considered necessary to improve the team experience throughout the feedback process.

Purpose of the study: This study aims to understand how feedback practices have been adopted by organizations and software development teams that work in the remote or hybrid model, investigate the perception of professionals who work in these teams, analyze the aspects that influence the success of the feedback and the changes that would improve the teams' experience. Understanding your experience and preferences about feedback practices is extremely valuable to our study. The data in this research consists of responding to a questionnaire anonymously.

Questionnaire response time: 8 - 10 minutes.

By clicking "Continue", you will start the questionnaire! We thank you very much in advance for your contribution.

Part 1 - General information

What is your age?

- Under 18
- 18 - 25
- 26 - 34
- 35 - 43
- 44 - 52
- More than 53

What is your gender?

- Male
- Female
- Non-binary
- Rather not to say

What is your last level of education?

- Secondary education (middle school, high school)
- Incomplete undergraduate education
- Complete undergraduate education
- Incomplete graduate education
- Master's degree
- Doctoral degree

What is your area of training?

- Computer Science
- Computer Engineer

- Information Systems
- Analysis and Systems Development
- Design
- Others...(option opened for users' customized responses)

How much professional experience do you have in the IT field?

- Under 1 year
- 1 - 3 years
- 3 - 5 years
- 5 - 7
- 44 - 52
- More than 5

Which of the levels below best describes your level in your current organization?

- Internship/Trainee
- Junior-level
- Mid-level
- Senior-level
- Leader/Manager

Which of the options below best describes your current role?

- Data Scientist/Data Engineering
- Developer/Software Engineering/Programmer
- DevOps Engineering/Infrastructure Engineering/Network Engineering
- Engineering Manager/IT Manager
- Project Manager/Product Owner/Scrum Master
- Requirements Analyst/Requirements Engineering
- Software Architect/Systems Architect
- Tester/Tests Leader/Tests Architect/QA Engineering
- Technical Support/IT Support
- UX/UI Designer
- Others...(option opened for users' customized responses)

Does your organization adopt an agile software development process?

- Yes
- No

What is the agile methodology(ies) adopted by your team?

- Scrum
- Kanban
- Lean
- XP (eXtreme Programming)
- FDD (Feature-Driven Development)
- Others... (option opened for users' customized responses)

What is the working model currently adopted by your organization?

- Remote
- Hybrid
- Traditional (In-office)

How often do you go to the office?

- I do not go to the office
- Once or twice a week

- Three or four times a week
- Every day
- Others... (option opened for users' customized responses)

Was this working model already adopted in your organization before the Covid-19 pandemic?
If not, what model was previously adopted?

- Yes
- No, the work model adopted was the traditional (in-office) one.
- No, the work model was the hybrid one.
- No, the work model was the remote one.
- I do not know

Part 2 - Understanding Feedback Practices

Do you like receiving feedback? If your answer is "It depends" or "I don't know", use the "Other" option to explain your choice.

- Yes
- No
- Others... (option opened for users' customized responses)

Is feedback a practice widely institutionalized by your organization?

- Yes
- No
- I do not know

Does your team adopt formal feedback practices daily?

- Yes
- No

Part 3 - Feedback Practices Preferences

How do you participate in the feedback process?

- I am evaluated only by my leader, and I do not evaluate anyone.
- I am evaluated only by my leader, and I do not evaluate him/her.
- I am evaluated only by my leader, and I evaluate all my team.
- I am evaluated by my entire team, and I evaluate all my team.
- Others... (option opened for users' customized responses)

Does your team adopt any specific feedback methodology/framework? If so, share with us what they are. (Ex: Feedback Canvas, Feedback 360)

Open-ended question

Does your team adopt any tools to support the feedback process? If yes, share with us the names of these tools.

Open-ended question

What is the frequency of feedback on your team?

- Weekly
- Biweekly
- Quarterly
- Semi-annual
- Annual
- Others... (open-ended option[for users' customized responses])

Part 4 - Improving Feedback Practices

Is there any form of informal feedback, which occurs subtly, as part of the work routine, within your team? Which one(s)?

Open-ended question

What feelings does the feedback process awaken in you?

- Joy
- Acknowledgment
- Excitement
- Happiness
- Motivation
- Recognition
- Satisfaction
- Tranquility
- Visibility
- Anxiety
- Unworthiness
- Uncertainty
- Insecurity
- Fear
- Nervousness
- Shame
- Sadness
- Others... (open-ended option[for users' customized responses])

What would you like to see in your feedback?

- Smaller interval between the feedback sessions
- Longer interval between sessions
- Written record of sessions
- Previous definition of the evaluated points
- Entire team participation
- Only leader Participation
- Building a Career Development Plan
- Use of a feedback-dedicated tool
- In-person feedback sessions
- Remote feedback-sessions
- Encouraging informal feedback daily (e.g. vouchers, discounts...)
- Others... (open-ended option[for users' customized responses])

Do you believe that the feedback process has influenced the development of your soft skills? If so, cite examples of some of these soft skills.

Open-ended question

Which of the following aspects related to your performance do you believe was/were impacted by the feedback process?

- None
- Productivity
- Security

- Delivery quality
- Delivery response time
- Remuneration
- Role progression
- Technical Enhancement
- Participation in events in my expertise area
- Others... (open-ended option[for users' customized responses])

What do you not like about the feedback process?

Open-ended question

In your opinion, what are the good practices that would improve your experience throughout the feedback process?

Open-ended question